

COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES ON THE STUDY OF DA'WA SCIENCE

**Islamic Guidance and Counseling Study Program
Class B5, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

**Teaching Lecturer
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**Faculty of Da'wa and Communication
Sunan Ampel State Islamic University
Surabaya, Indonesia, December 2022**

Collection of the Article Novelties on the Study of Da'wa Science

Islamic Guidance and Counseling Study Program

Class B5, Odd Semester of 2022-2023

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1st Publication: December 2022

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7454296

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PREFACE

This novelties collection is an output that shines from article reviews on da'wa published by scientific journals. This collection is the result of the "Da'wa Science" lecture at the Islamic Guidance and Counseling Study Program, Faculty of Da'wa and Communication, Sunan Ampel State Islamic University, Surabaya, Indonesia, on Odd Semester of 2022-2023. The reviewers are the students concerned in class B5.

The teaching lecturer guides the reviewers who are divided into 12 teams with different articles. Each team reviewed one article. The review includes the description of the article that was reviewed, the description of previous researches, the discussion of the review, the preparation of novelty from the article abstract, and the contribution of article to the development of science insights, especially the study programs concerned.

The presence of this collection marked the progress of student's study since they were in the first semester in their S1 study range. This is a valuable achievement savings for them and can be an important rising ladder in their intellectual progress during the study period and at the next level of study.

On the end, the teaching lecturer conveyed congratulations and high appreciation to all students who contributed to this collection. Hopefully they can all achieve the best achievements in their studies with great useful knowledge for religion and people at large. *Amin.*

Surabaya, January 9, 2023

Lecturer & Reviewers

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**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Da'wa Science, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

- Review Number : #1-B5-22
- Article Title : Filosofi Dakwah dalam Perspektif Alquran
- Author(s) : Sahrul Sahrul
- Publishing Information : Journal Analytica Islamica 2, no. 1 (2013): 53–68.
<http://jurnal.uinsu.ac.id/index.php/analytica/article/view/394>
- Subject of the Study : Da'wa Science
- Study Period : Odd Semester of 2022-2023
- Study Program, Class : Islamic Guidance and Counseling, B5
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Pemahaman filosofi dakwah dalam perspektif al-Qur'an yang mencakup nilai-nilai kebenaran yang dikandung oleh al-Qur'an tidaklah dibatasi oleh ruang dan waktu, bersifat rasional, artinya logis atau masuk akal, universal bersifat umum atau rahmatan lil'alamin, objektif, amar makruf dan nahi munkar dan bukanlah amar munkar dan nahi makruf serta bersifat egalitarian.
- English Novelty : To achieve an understanding of the philosophy of da'wa in the perspective of the Koran which includes the values of truth contained in the Koran that are not limited by space and time, are rational, meaning logical or reasonable, universal in nature or rahmatan lil'alamin, objective, amar makruf and nahi munkar and not amar munkar and nahi makruf and are egalitarian.

Reviewer Team

Reviewer 1

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Reviewer 2

Name : Prima Annisa Lentera Hati
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**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Da'wa Science, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

- Review Number : #2-B5-22
- Article Title : Prinsip-Prinsip Metode Dakwah menurut al-Qur'an
- Author(s) : Aliyudin Aliyudin
- Publishing Information : Ilmu Dakwah: Academic Journal for Homiletic Studies 5, no. 15 (2010): 1007–1022.
<https://journal.uinsgd.ac.id/index.php/idajhs/article/view/431>
- Subject of the Study : Da'wa Science
- Study Period : Odd Semester of 2022-2023
- Study Program, Class : Islamic Guidance and Counseling, B5
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Prinsip metode dakwah ada 3 yang disebutkan dalam al-Qur'an. Metode dakwah mempunyai makna yaitu menyemangati, melakukan pendekatan, dan sesuatu yang dapat di capai dengan tujuan yang pasti dan benar kepada sang maha pencipta. Oleh karena itu menurut Nazaruddin Razak, proses dakwah tidak dapat berjalan dengan efisien tanpa metode.
- English Novelty : There are 3 principles of da'wa methods which are mentioned in the Qur'an. The da'wa method has the meaning of encouraging, approaching, and something that can be achieved with a definite and true purpose to the almighty creator. Therefore, according to Nazaruddin Razak, the da'wa process cannot run efficiently without a method.

Reviewer Team

Reviewer 1

Name : Rima Wardatul Ma'rufah

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**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Da'wa Science, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

- Review Number : #3-B5-22
- Article Title : Sistem Interaksi antar Unsur dalam Sistem Dawah dan Implikasinya dalam Gerakan Dakwah
- Author(s) : Anas Habibi Ritonga
- Publishing Information : Hikmah 14, no. 1 (2020): 87–102.
<http://194.31.53.129/index.php/Hik/article/view/2033>
- Subject of the Study : Da'wa Science
- Study Period : Odd Semester of 2022-2023
- Study Program, Class : Islamic Guidance and Counseling, B5
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Interaksi sosial dalam proses dakwah ini ditujukan untuk mempengaruhi *mad'u* yang akan membawa perubahan sikap prilaku seperti mempererat tali perasaudaraan dengan silaturahmi dan meneladani kepribadaian yang baik dari sang pendakwah. Tujuan dakwah adalah mencapai kebahagiaan dunia dan akhirat.
- English Novelty : Social interaction in the process of preaching is aimed at influencing *mad'u* which will bring about changes in behavior such as strengthening kinship ties with friendship and emulating the good personality of the preacher. The goal of da'wa is to achieve happiness in the world and the hereafter.

Reviewer Team

Reviewer 1

Name : Riyadh Ridha

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**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Da'wa Science, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

- Review Number : #4-B5-22
- Article Title : Pendekatan Dakwah Melalui 'Konsep Cinta Muslim'dalam Menangani Masalah Sosial
- Author(s) : Syaidatun Nazirah Abu Zahrin, Rezki Perdana Sawai, Mohd Shahrul Faizie Zaini, and Allawati Kasri
- Publishing Information : Al-Hikmah 6, no. 1 (2014): 21–34.
<http://spaj.ukm.my/jalhikmah/index.php/jalhikmah/article/view/82>.
- Subject of the Study : Da'wa Science
- Study Period : Odd Semester of 2022-2023
- Study Program, Class : Islamic Guidance and Counseling, B5
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Cinta kepada Allah dan cinta karena Allah dapat mengantarkan cinta yang boleh membawa gejala sosial, dan oleh karena itu mendidik konsep cinta Muslim kepada remaja Islam amatlah penting dan boleh diterapkan melalui berbagai mekanisme dakwah. Antara media cetak, media massa, ceramah, syarahan dan forum, facebook, twitter, instagram dan sebagainya. Tetapi permasalahannya di sini para remaja zaman sekarang belum bisa memanfaatkan mekanisme dakwah tersebut dengan benar. Oleh karena itulah betapa pentingnya untuk bisa memahaminya.
- English Novelty : Love for God and love because God can deliver love that can bring social phenomena, and therefore educating the concept of Muslim love for Islamic teenagers is very important and may be applied through various da'wa mechanisms. Between print media, mass media, lectures, sharing and forums, Facebook, Twitter,

Instagram and so on. But the problem here is that teenagers today have not been able to take advantage of the propaganda mechanism correctly. That's why how important it is to be able to understand it.

Reviewer Team

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Name : Safira Fadella Syaharani

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**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Da'wa Science, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

- Review Number : #5-B5-22
- Article Title : Cyberdakwah: Internet sebagai Media Baru dalam Sistem Komunikasi Dakwah Islam
- Author(s) : Ridwan Rustandi
- Publishing Information : NALAR: Jurnal Peradaban dan Pemikiran Islam 3, no. 2 (2019): 84–95. <https://e-journal.iain-palangkaraya.ac.id/index.php/nalar/article/view/1678>
- Subject of the Study : Da'wa Science
- Study Period : Odd Semester of 2022-2023
- Study Program, Class : Islamic Guidance and Counseling, B5
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Fenomena cyberdakwah secara teoritik dipandang sebagai metode kontemporer dalam penyebaran pesan dakwah. Penggunaan media internet sebagai media baru dalam dakwah Islam membuka peluang untuk menyebarkan pesan-pesan dakwah secara masif dan signifikan.
- English Novelty : The theoretical Cyberda'wa phenomenon is seen as a contemporary method in the distribution of da'wa messages. The use of internet media as a new media in Islamic da'wa opens opportunities to disseminate massive and significant preaching messages.

Reviewer Team

Reviewer 1

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**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Da'wa Science, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

- Review Number : #6-B5-22
- Article Title : Teknologi Informasi sebagai Media Komunikasi
Pesan Dakwah
- Author(s) : Rosmalina, Asriyanti
- Publishing Information : Orasi: Jurnal Dakwah dan Komunikasi 10, no.
1 (2019): 66–73.
<https://syekhnurjati.ac.id/jurnal/index.php/orasi/article/view/5139>
- Subject of the Study : Da'wa Science
- Study Period : Odd Semester of 2022-2023
- Study Program, Class : Islamic Guidance and Counseling, B5
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Ormas Islam tidak ketinggalan untuk menciptakan situs-situs resmi atau bahkan media-media sosial sebagai sarana menyampaikan dakwah. Melalui teknologi informasi tersebut, semua orang dapat mengakses bermacam informasi dari berbagai sumber di seluruh dunia.
- English Novelty : Islamic organizations are not left behind in creating official websites or even social media as a means of conveying da'wa. Through this information technology, everyone can access various information from various sources around the world.

Reviewer Team

Reviewer 1

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Reviewer 2

Name : Zuhair Al-Asady

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Name : Zulia Rahmawati

Student ID Number : 04040322163

**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Da'wa Science, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

- Review Number : #7-B5-22
- Article Title : Model Dakwah dalam Pelayanan Pasien
- Author(s) : Reza Ahmadiansah
- Publishing Information : IJIP: Indonesian Journal of Islamic Psychology
1, no.2 (2019): 215–242.
<https://ijtihad.iainsalatiga.ac.id/index.php/ijip/article/view/3819>.
- Subject of the Study : Da'wa Science
- Study Period : Odd Semester of 2022-2023
- Study Program, Class : Islamic Guidance and Counseling, B5
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Model dakwah yang digunakan dalam melayani pasiennya bimbingan dengan mengedepankan spiritualitas agama seperti zikir, doa, dan sebagainya.
- English Novelty : The da'wa model used in serving patients is guidance by prioritizing religious spirituality such as *dhikr*, prayer, and so on.

Reviewer Team

Reviewer 1

Name : Azlia Isaura Machsya
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Reviewer 3

Name : Inayah Trinurkholifah
Student ID Number : 04040322166

**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Da'wa Science, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

- Review Number : #8-B5-22
- Article Title : Paradigma Dakwah Gafatar di Dunia Maya dalam Perspektif Shifting Paradigm
- Author(s) : Fatmawati Fatmawati and Vicky Diania.
- Publishing Information : Madania: Jurnal Kajian Keislaman 20, no. 2 (2016):183–196.
<https://ejournal.iainbengkulu.ac.id/index.php/madania/article/view/167>
- Subject of the Study : Da'wa Science
- Study Period : Odd Semester of 2022-2023
- Study Program, Class : Islamic Guidance and Counseling, B5
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Gafatar telah mengubah ideologi gerakannya secara normal science yang menjadi daya tarik audien dakwah dengan melakukan kegiatan sosial kemasyarakatan, melahirkan ajaran doktrinal dalam kubangan normal science-nya menjadi paradigma baru berupa kegiatan sosial kemasyarakatan.
- English Novelty : Gafatar has changed the ideology of its movement to normal science which is the main attraction for da'wa audiences by carrying out social activities, gave birth to doctrinal teachings in the normal science puddle into a new paradigm in the form of social activities.

Reviewer Team

Reviewer 1

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Reviewer 2

Name : Mohammad Amin

Student ID Number : 04040322168

Reviewer 3

Name : Nadia Nurul Rahmawati

Student ID Number : 04040322169

**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Da'wa Science, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

- Review Number : #9-B5-22
- Article Title : Peranan Da'i dalam Mengatasi Problem Dakwah Kontemporer
- Author(s) : M Ikhsan Ghozali
- Publishing Information : Mawa'izh: Jurnal Dakwah dan Pengembangan Sosial Kemanusiaan 8, no. 2 (2017): 293–307.
<https://jurnal.lp2msasbabel.ac.id/index.php/ma/w/article/view/777>
- Subject of the Study : Da'wa Science
- Study Period : Odd Semester of 2022-2023
- Study Program, Class : Islamic Guidance and Counseling, B5
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Para *da'i* harus mampu “membangkitkan” dan “mengaktualisasikan” hakikat dan signifikansi dakwah, baik objek dan sasaran, metodologi, manajemen kelembagaan, maupun sumber daya manusia. Selanjutnya, sebagai agent of social change, para *da'i* mampu membawa perubahan sosial, kehidupan berbangsa dan beragama ke arah yang lebih baik serta mewujudkan Islam yang rahmatan lil 'alamin.
- English Novelty : Preachers must be able to "ground" and "actualize" the nature and the significance of da'wa, both object and target, methodology, institutional management, as well as human resources. Furthermore, as agents of social change, the preachers able to bring social change, national and religious life in a positive direction better and realize Islam that is rahmatan lil 'alamin.

Reviewer Team

Reviewer 1

Name : Nadzifah Nailil Izzah

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Reviewer 2

Name : Nur Fadilatul Umaroh

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Reviewer 3

Name : Rukhoinah

Student ID Number : 04040322172

**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Da'wa Science, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

Review Number	: #10-B5-22
Article Title	: Problematika Dakwah Kontemporer: Tinjauan Faktor Internal dan Eksternal
Author(s)	: Dahrun Sajadi
Publishing Information	: Al-Risalah: Jurnal Studi Agama dan Pemikiran Islam 11, no. 2 (2020): 93–109. https://uia.ejournal.id/alrisalah/article/view/821
Subject of the Study	: Da'wa Science
Study Period	: Odd Semester of 2022-2023
Study Program, Class	: Islamic Guidance and Counseling, B5
Lecturer	: Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
Indonesian Novelty	: Problematika dakwah kontemporer yang ditinjau dari faktor internal berupa ketidakmampuan umat Islam dalam melakukan inovasi serta faktor eksternal yang berupa serangan pemikiran seperti Komunisme dan Syi'ah.
English Novelty	: The problems of contemporary da'wa in terms of internal factors are the inability of Muslims to innovate as well as external factors in the form of thought attacks such as Communism and Syi'ah .

Reviewer Team

Reviewer 1

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Reviewer 3

Name : Ummi Kulsum

Student ID Number : 04040322175

**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Da'wa Science, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

- Review Number : #11-B5-22
- Article Title : Integrasi Dakwah Islam dengan Ilmu Komunikasi
- Author(s) : Suhaimi Suhaimi
- Publishing Information : Miqot: Jurnal Ilmu-ilmu Keislaman 37, no. 1 (2013):214–228.
<http://jurnalmiqotojs.uinsu.ac.id/index.php/jurnalmiqot/article/view/81>
- Subject of the Study : Da'wa Science
- Study Period : Odd Semester of 2022-2023
- Study Program, Class : Islamic Guidance and Counseling, B5
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Terdapat kesamaan status antara sarjana dakwah Islam dengan sarjana ilmu komunikasi karena dakwah Islam secara akademis dapat diintegrasikan dengan ilmu komunikasi menjadi ilmu komunikasi Islam.
- English Novelty : There is a similarity in status between Islamic da'wa scholars and communication science graduates because Islamic da'wa academically can be integrated with communication science to become Islamic communication science.

Reviewer Team

Reviewer 1

Name : Aisyah Husna Az Zahra
Hulu

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Reviewer 2

Name : Farisah Habibah Husna

Student ID Number : 04050322177

Reviewer 3

Name : Muhammad Nor Syahwal
Arrafiqi

Student ID Number : 04050322178

**COLLECTION OF THE ARTICLE NOVELTIES
on the Study of Da'wa Science, Odd Semester of 2022-2023**

- Review Number : #12-B5-22
- Article Title : Perkembangan Keilmuan Dakwah Islam dalam Tinjauan Metodologis
- Author(s) : Rr. Suhartini
- Publishing Information : .Islamic Da'wa Development in Europe and Asia Pacific (International Conference Proceeding), 5–14. Surabaya: UIN Sunan Ampel, 2016. <http://digilib.uinsby.ac.id/36226/>
- Subject of the Study : Da'wa Science
- Study Period : Odd Semester of 2022-2023
- Study Program, Class : Islamic Guidance and Counseling, B5
- Lecturer : Dr. Sokhi Huda, M.Ag
- Indonesian Novelty : Proses berkembangnya ilmu dakwah berkembang dengan pertumbuhan dirinya sendiri, yaitu melalui proses komunikasi dalam aktifitas dakwah, komunikasi antar unsur dakwah, dan proses konversi sebagai dampak kegiatan dakwah. Perkembangan ilmu dakwah ini berkembang dengan disiplin keilmuan dalam sebuah konteks penelitian yang dilakukan.
- English Novelty : The process of developing the science of da'wa develops growth itself, namely through the process of communication in da'wa activities, communication between da'wa elements, and processes conversion as a result of da'wa activities. Development of science This da'wa develops with scientific disciplines in the context of the research conducted.

Reviewer Team

Reviewer 1

Name : Muhammad Taufiq Asbah Usman

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Reviewer 2

Name : Shima Qurrota Ayunin Syah

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Reviewer 3

Name : Tauhid Imaduddin

Student ID Number : 04050322181

This novelties collection is an output that shines from from article reviews on da'wa published by scientific journals. This collection is the result of the "Da'wa Science" lecture at the Islamic Guidance and Counseling Study Program, Faculty of Da'wa and Communication, Sunan Ampel State Islamic University, Surabaya, Indonesia, on Odd Semester of 2022-2023. The reviewers are the students concerned in class B5.

The presence of this collection marked the progress of student's study since they were in the first semester in their S1 study range. This is a valuable achievement savings for them and can be an important rising ladder in their intellectual progress during the study period and at the next level of study.